

Interpretation of the Effect of Methanol on the Aquation of Sodium Monobromoethylenediaminetetraacetatocobaltate(III) in Terms of D_s^{-1} , E_T^N , X_{Org} , A_X , B_X and Δg Values

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Manuscript received 24 June 1996, revised 22 August 1997, accepted 3 October 1997

The kinetics of formation of ethylenediaminetetraacetatocobaltate(III) ion, $[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]^-$ from $[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})]^-$ has been investigated both in pure water and in water + methanol mixtures in the temperature range 45–55° at $I = 0.04 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, where I is ionic strength. The first order rate constant varies with the variation of methanol content in the solvent mixture. From the plots of $\log k$ against D_s^{-1} (reciprocal of the bulk dielectric constant of the medium), E_T^N (normalized values of solvatochromic solvation parameter) and $X_{\text{CH}_3\text{OH}}$ (mole fraction of methanol), a suitable interpretation has been offered for the nature of the curve obtained in each case in terms of modification of water structure, preferential solvation and acidity and basicity parameters associated with the solvent mixtures.

The ligand ethylenediaminetetraacetate, EDTA^{4-} , is hexadentate, but it also forms quinquedentate complexes. The sixth coordination position of cobalt(III) is occupied by a ligand which may be a neutral or a simple anion. Complexes of the type, $M[(\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{X})]$, where M is a monovalent metal and X is bromide, chloride, nitrite or azide, have been synthesized¹⁻³. Kinetics and mechanism of formation of $M[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]$ from these complexes have been studied in aqueous medium.

Morris and Busch⁴ studied the rates of acid hydrolysis of cobalt(III) complexes of pentadentate ethylenediaminetetraacetate and suggested three most likely mechanisms, viz. I_{NS} , $\text{S}_{\text{N}}1$ and $\text{S}_{\text{N}}2$. These authors reported that the reaction follows first order kinetics and it is pH-independent over the pH range 1–3. Shimi and Higginson⁵ suggested that the formation of $[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]^-$ from $[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{Br}]^-$ follows unimolecular path in which $[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]^-$ is the primary reaction product. Dyke and Higginson^{6,7} dealt with the kinetics of formation of $[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]^-$ from $[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})\text{Cl}]^{2-}$ and its conjugate acid, $[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{Cl}]^-$. Based on Hg^{II} -catalyzed reaction, it was suggested^{6,7} that $[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ is initially formed from $[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{Cl}]^-$. However, these authors, based on the available evidence, could not conclude that $[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]^-$ is the only primary product in the uncatalyzed reaction. Balasubramanian and Natarajan³ made a detailed study on the reactions of sodium monoazidoethylenediaminetetraacetatocobaltate(III) and here the authors have proposed a scheme for the formation of $[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]^-$ from $[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{Br}]^-$.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complex, sodium monobromoethylenediaminetetraacetatocobaltate(III), are in agreement with the calculated values ($\text{Na}[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{Br}] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$ calcd : Co, 11.67; Br, 15.82. Found : Co, 11.47; Br, 14.36%). The electronic spectra of the title complex

showed two charge transfer bands at 235.01 and 268.5 nm with ϵ values 14.779 and $14.336 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively, and one ligand field band at 592.01 nm with ϵ value $236 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Fujita and Shimura⁸ reported the occurrence of a band at 588.0 nm with ϵ value $218.7 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$ which is in good agreement with the value obtained in the present investigation. However, these authors did not report the appearance of any shoulder in the region 380–400 nm. But Natarajan and Endicott⁹ reported a shoulder in this region. The spectrum of the complex recorded in the present investigation also shows a shoulder at 382 nm. The ir spectrum of the complex shows a strong absorption band at 1635 cm^{-1} which is attributed¹⁰ to the presence of three coordinated carboxyl groups. The weak absorption band appearing at 1735 cm^{-1} is assigned to free carboxyl group. The $\text{p}K_a$ of the complex was determined by pH-titrimetric method and is found to be 3.03, which agrees well with the reported^{1,11} value of *ca* 3.

The rate constants for the formation of $[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]^-$ from $[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{Br}]^-$ in water were determined at different initial concentrations of the complex, viz. 0.6×10^{-4} , 0.8×10^{-4} , 1.0×10^{-4} and $1.2 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The rate constants, $k \times 10^5 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$ are 3.00, 3.08, 3.14 and 3.09 respectively, suggesting that the reaction is first order with respect to the substrate. The effects of ionic strength and pH on the rate constant have also been studied. At 45° and at pH 2.40, the rate constant $k \times 10^5 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$ in media of different ionic strengths 4×10^{-3} , 9×10^{-3} , 14×10^{-3} , 24×10^{-3} and $44 \times 10^{-3} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$ are 2.98, 2.98, 3.07, 3.03 and 3.00 respectively, indicating that the rate constant is independent of ionic strength. At 45° and in a medium of ionic strength $4.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$, the values of $k \times 10^5 \text{ (s}^{-1}\text{)}$ at pH 1.50, 1.80, 2.10, 2.40 and 2.60 are 3.03, 2.92, 2.97, 3.04 and 3.00 respectively, suggesting that the reaction is independent of pH over the pH range 1.50–2.60.

The plots of $\log k$ against the reciprocal of the bulk dielectric constant of the media, (D_s^{-1}), where D_s^{-1} values

were obtained by interpolation from the data published by Akerlof¹² at three different temperatures, viz. 45, 50 and 55°, yielded reasonably good straight-lines indicating that the results are in good agreement with the Laidler-Landskroener equation¹³⁻¹⁵. The linearity suggests the presence of only little influence of solvent structure as well as solvent-solute interaction. The slope of the plots at 45, 50 and 55° are -110.2, -107.0 and -94.0 respectively. This type of linear plot with a large negative slope suggests dissociative mechanism¹⁶.

Several attempts were made to correlate empirical parameters of a solvent with its polarity and its solvation characteristics and one such attempt has been the use of E_T values. Normalized E_T values, E_T^N , are preferred to E_T (30) values because the former values have been formulated using tetramethylsilane and water as reference solvents¹⁷. In the present investigation, E_T^N values were calculated using interpolation equation (Equation 1) given by Bosch and Roses¹⁸ and are used for plotting $\log k$ against E_T^N values,

$$E_T^N = \frac{E_T^N(1) + x_2 \left(\frac{f_2}{f_1} \right) E_T^N(2) - E_T^N(1)}{1 + x_2 \left(\frac{f_2}{f_1} - 1 \right)} \quad (1)$$

where, E_T^N , $E_T^N(1)$ and $E_T^N(2)$ are the normalized values of empirical solvent polarity parameters of a binary solvent mixture, component solvent (1) and component solvent (2) respectively, and f_1 and f_2 are the proportionality constants, representing tendencies of solvents 1 and 2 to solvate the standard solvatochromic dye, and x_2 represents the mole fraction of the more polar component. The values of $E_T^N(1)$, $E_T^N(2)$ and f_2/f_1 reported for water + methanol mixtures are 0.769, 1.00 and 0.260 respectively.

Fig. 1. Plots of $\log k$ against E_T^N for the formation of $[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]^-$ from $[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{Br}]$ in water + methanol mixtures at (○) 45°, (●) 50° and (□) 55°.

The plot of $\log k$ against E_T^N is curved (Fig. 1) and the nature of the curve can be accounted for in terms of some overall function of polarity¹⁰. With a view to examining further the influence of methanol on rate, a plot was drawn between $\log k$ and mole fraction of methanol and found to be linear. The dependence of rate on mole fraction of methanol can be interpreted in terms of acidity and basicity parameters of water + methanol mixtures. In the expressions,

$$A_x = A_{\text{org}} X_{\text{org}} + A_w (1 - X_{\text{org}}) \quad (2)$$

$$B_x = B_{\text{org}} X_{\text{org}} + B_w (1 - X_{\text{org}}) \quad (3)$$

A_{org} and B_{org} represent the acidity and basicity parameters of pure organic solvents, and A_w and B_w the respective parameters of pure water. Equations (2) and (3) reveal linear variation of acidity and basicity parameters of water + methanol mixtures with the mole fraction of methanol. The acidity parameter of a pure solvent is a measure of its anion-solvating tendency, its hydrogen-bonding acidity or its electrophilicity, whereas the basicity parameter is a measure of its cation-solvating tendency, its hydrogen-bonding basicity or its nucleophilicity. Dash and Dash²⁰ proposed the following equation relating rate constant of a reaction in a mixed solvent medium with its acidity and basicity parameters,

$$\log k_s = l_1 X_{\text{org}} + l_2 + C \quad (4)$$

where, $l_1 = a (A_{\text{org}} - A_w) + b (B_{\text{org}} - B_w)$ and $l_2 = a A_w + b B_w$, where a and b are reaction constants. Substituting the assigned values of acidity and basicity parameters by Swain *et al.*²¹ in equation (4), three authors²² showed that the plot of $\log k$ against mole fraction of methanol in the solvent mixture is linear with negative slope for the study of a similar reaction. The present study also shows a similar trend.

Based on the model developed by Marcus²³, the following expression was obtained to account for the medium effect on the process of transition from initial state to transition state,

$$\log k_s = \log k_w - \frac{1}{2.303RT} [\Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{t.s.}) - \Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{i.s.})]_{\text{s} \leftarrow \text{w}} \quad (5)$$

where, k_s and k_w represent the rate constants in mixed aqueous organic solvent and water respectively. The term $[\Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{t.s.}) - \Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{i.s.})]_{\text{s} \leftarrow \text{w}}$ denotes the standard free energy of transfer of the transition state relative to the standard free energy of transfer of the initial state from water to water + organic solvent mixtures. A dimensionless parameter, viz. preferential solvation parameter (g) in the form of the following expression was also defined²⁴,

$$g = \frac{[\Delta G_t^\ddagger(\text{i.})]_{X_{\text{org}}}}{RT X_{\text{org}} (1 - X_{\text{org}})} \quad (6)$$

where,

$$[\Delta G_i^E(i)]_{X_{org}} = [\Delta G_i^0(i)]_{s \leftarrow w} - X_{org} [\Delta G_i^0(i)]_{org \leftarrow w} \quad (7)$$

The following expression was also suggested by combining *g* and excess free energy of transfer,

$$\log k_s = \log k_w - aX_{org} + bX_{org}^2 \quad (8)$$

where, $a = \frac{\Delta g + c/RT}{2.303}$, $b = \frac{\Delta g}{2.303}$

$$c = [\Delta G_i^0(t.s) - \Delta G_i^0(i.s)]_{org \leftarrow w} \text{ and } \Delta g = [g(t.s) - g(i.s)]$$

The values of rate constant were fitted to equation (8) by a least-square computer programme to obtain the values of *a* and *b* and using these values, the values of Δg and *c* were evaluated (Table 2). The adjustable parameter *a* is a measure of relative solvational propensity of the transition state with respect to that of the initial state and it is also related to the acidity and basicity parameters of the solvent mixture²⁴. Although direct measurement of $[\Delta G_i^0(t.s) - \Delta G_i^0(i.s)]_{org \leftarrow w}$ is not possible, it is possible to estimate its value from equation (8). A close examination of the data (Table 2) reveals that Δg is positive for the reaction, studied at all temperatures. A positive Δg value suggests that the solvation cosphere of the transition state is modified preferentially. However, the magnitude is small indicating little significance of preferential solvation as is evident from linear plot of $\log k$ against X_{CH_3OH} . The values of Δg also reveal that even that little significance decreases with the increase of temperature. The linearity observed for the plot of $\log k$ against mole fraction of methanol can be accounted for in terms of substitutional dissolution of methanol. Eley²⁵ suggested that only $9.0 \times 10^{-6} \text{ m}^3$ of empty space is available in one mole of water due to the formation of clusters. Cavities are formed in these clusters and these cavities can accommodate small molecules, such as methanol, without affecting the free water molecules²⁶ and hence $\log k$ varies linearly with mole fraction of methanol.

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF MOLE FRACTION OF METHANOL ON THE RATE CONSTANT FOR THE FORMATION OF $[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]^-$ FROM $[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{Br}]^-$ AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

X_{CH_3OH}	$k \times 10^3 (\text{s}^{-1})$		
	45°	50°	55°
0	3.14	5.27	7.69
0.023	2.56	4.68	7.61
0.046	2.11	4.04	6.12
0.072	2.04	3.59	6.05
0.098	1.84	3.49	5.06
0.127	1.80	3.07	4.55
0.158	1.52	2.69	4.26
0.190	1.47	2.49	3.99
0.225	1.18	2.01	3.16
0.263	1.04	1.72	2.60
0.304	0.83	1.59	2.41

TABLE 2—CALCULATED VALUES OF PARAMETERS *a*, *b*, Δg AND *c* OF EQUATION(8) FOR THE FORMATION OF $[\text{Co}(\text{EDTA})]^-$ FROM $[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{Br}]^-$ IN WATER + METHANOL MIXTURES

Temp. °C	<i>a</i>	<i>b</i>	Δg	<i>c</i>
45	2.235	1.715	3.947	-3.721
50	1.998	0.942	2.169	-4.575
55	1.643	0.212	0.488	-5.824

The logarithm of rate constants in water + methanol mixtures at pH 2.40, ionic strength 0.04 *M* and at three different temperatures were plotted against the values of Grunwald-Winstein parameter (Y_{ButCl}) obtained by interpolation from the data published by Fainberg and Winstein²⁷ and the linear plots suggest that the mechanism of the reaction in the present study is comparable to that of the solvolysis of *t*-butyl chloride, which is a well-known S_N1 reaction. Such plots have been found to be linear for aquations of majority of chloroaminocobalt(III) complexes²⁸ in water + organic solvent mixture media with the value of *m* = 0.3. The low value of *m* for the hydrolysis of chloroaminocobalt(III) complexes compared to *m* = 1 for the solvolysis of the model compound, *t*-butyl chloride, might be due to the fact that the cobalt(III)-chloride bond is ionic and hence less dependent on the solvent for bond dissociation.

Experimental

Methanol (AnalaR) was purified²⁹. Glacial acetic acid, disodium salt of ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid, perchloric acid and sodium perchlorate were of A.R. grade. Sodium monobromoethylenediaminetetraacetatocobaltate(III), $\text{Na}[\text{Co}(\text{HEDTA})\text{Br}] \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}$, was prepared by the reported procedure¹. Electronic spectra were recorded on a CECIL 5501 spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Shimadzu 408 spectrophotometer.

Kinetic study : An aqueous solution of the complex ($1.0 \times 10^{-4} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) with known pH (2.40) and ionic strength ($4.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) was thermostatted. The decrease in absorbance was monitored at 270 nm under pseudo-first order condition. First order plots were found to be linear. Kinetic runs were repeated with a view to studying the effect of ionic strength, pH and temperature on the rate of the reaction. Similar experiments were performed in water + methanol mixtures of varying compositions at different temperatures, viz. 45, 50 and 55°. The rate constants are the average of duplicate measurements, showing reproducibility of $\pm 2\%$.

Acknowledgement

The authors acknowledge the Management, Principal and Head of Department of Chemistry, Bishop Heber College, Tiruchirappalli, for facilities, and U.G.C., New Delhi, for the award of fellowship under the FIP scheme.

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